



Supplementary figure 2 Antibody levels in EIRA RA cases based on smoking status. IgM RF (A), IgG RF (B) and IgA RF (C) levels were significantly increased in current and former smokers compared to never smokers, and in current smokers compared to former smokers. Anti-CCP2 IgG levels (D) were significantly increased in current and former smokers compared to never smokers, but not in current smokers compared to former smokers. The red horizontal lines indicate median antibody levels. Y-axes show antibody levels on a logarithmic scale. Never = never smoked; current = current smoker; former = former smoker.